

Supplementary Tables titles

Table S1. Literature review summarising presence or absence of phenotypic associations in birds for the focal candidate genes . Search terms in Google Scholar (December 2021) were: each of the candidate genes AND “birds” . For example: “CLOCK” AND “birds”.

Table S2. Complete dataset

Table S3. Summary of genetic and genomic resources by population used in this study

Table S4. Allele summary statistics per population

Table S5. NGSadmix log likelihoods for the whole dataset, ANZO and Southern Melanesia. Lower numbers represent a higher fit to the data.

Table S6. Population-level covariance matrix generated using WGS data. This matrix was used to control for population structure in the Bayesian linear mixed models

Table S7. Gene flow levels representing the fraction of individuals in population *i* (columns) migrating into population *j* (rows). In bold those estimates for which the 0.5% of the posterior probability density does not overlap with zero

Table S8. *brms* models output for tests of differences in candidate gene variation among populations. In bold, those populations for which the credibility intervals do not overlap with zero

Table S9. *brms* models output for tests of differences in candidate gene variation between migrants and non-migrants from Tasmania

Table S10. *brms* linear mixed models results. None of the models reveal a clear effect of our variables of interest in allele length. This can be seen in the wide error relative to the estimate and the lower 95% credibility intervals overlapping zero. The model comparison with loo indicates that none of the model is better than the other

Table S11. Results of *mcp* models. Estimates indicate a reduction of 5 bp with increasing population age and the same increase with dispersal index. Model comparison reveals that the model including our variables of interests performs better than the null model